

Simulation of the Solar System Using Leapfrog Integration Method*

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Abstract

This study used the leapfrog method to produce ephemerides for the solar system. The position data produced by the leapfrog method was compared to JPL's published ephemerides. Additionally, the properties of the leapfrog method were investigated. The study found that while the leapfrog method conserved energy and angular momentum of the whole system, the average positional difference with JPL increased over time. These findings contribute to the understanding of the method's strengths and limitations for celestial mechanics simulations.

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1 Introduction

Predicting the motion of the planets has always been of interest to humankind. Many brilliant minds have tried to tackle what appears to be a complex problem. However, Feynman's chapter [4] on the motion of the planets introduces a simple and elegant solution to this intricate problem by taking advantage of the Leapfrog integration method. Building upon this foundation, a Fortran code was developed to simulate planetary motion [5]. This study aims to use this Fortran code to analyze the leapfrog method and its limits by comparing it to NASA JPL's already-provided ephemerides.

2 Newton's Laws of Motion and Gravitation

Newton's three laws of motion are as follows;

- 1. An object at rest remains at rest, and an object in motion remains in motion at constant speed and in a straight line unless acted on by an unbalanced force.
- 2. The acceleration of an object depends on the mass of the object and the amount of force applied.

$$\frac{d\vec{P}}{dt} = \vec{F}$$

where:

$$\vec{P} = m\vec{v}$$

If the mass of the object remains the same, the formula can be simplified as;

$$\vec{F} = \frac{d(m\vec{v})}{dt} = \frac{d(m)}{dt}\vec{v} + \frac{d(\vec{v})}{dt}m = \frac{d(\vec{v})}{dt}m = m\vec{a}$$

- 3. Whenever one object exerts a force on another object, the second object exerts an equal and opposite force on the first.

Newton's law of gravitation is given as [6];

$$\vec{F} = -\frac{GM_1M_2}{r^2}\hat{r} \quad (1)$$

Equating Newton's second law to Newton's law of gravity, we get the following expression for the acceleration of a planet.

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{F} &= -\frac{GM_1M_2}{r^2}\hat{r} = M_2\vec{a}_2 \\ \vec{a}_2 &= -\frac{GM_1}{r^2}\hat{r} = -\frac{k_1}{r^2}\hat{r} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where:

$$k = GM_1$$

$k \equiv$ gravitational parameter

In the calculation of the motion of the planets, this exact equation will be used to calculate the acceleration of each planet. It is important to note that according to these calculations, objects are approximated as very tiny moving points in space. Because the planets are so far away from each other they will appear as point masses to one another.

3 Leapfrog

On October 24th, 1961, a few months after Yuri Gagarin's successful launch into space, Sec 9.7 of Feynman's Lecture on Physics, Planetary Motions, was taught to the freshman students of Caltech [2]. In the class, Feynman starts the lesson with a classical spring-mass example. The reason behind this decision is quite simple. The motion of the spring-mass system is easy to describe with Newton's laws of motion. The analytical solution of the system can be obtained and used to test the effectiveness of any numerical method. Initially, he describes the motion of the mass using the numerical Euler's integration method [1, 7]. He derives the formulation in the following way [1];

The force on a mass applied by a spring is given as: [1]

$$\vec{F} = -k\vec{x}$$

Neglecting the gravity, the acceleration of the mass is found as: [1]

$$m\vec{a} = -k\vec{x}$$

$$\vec{a} = -\frac{k}{m}\vec{x}$$

To simplify the calculation process, Feynman takes $\frac{k}{m}$ as 1. [1]

$$\vec{a} = -\vec{x}$$

Given the initial conditions, x_0 and v_0 ;

$$\vec{a}_0 = -\vec{x}_0$$

$$\vec{v}_1 = \vec{v}_0 + \vec{a}_0\Delta t$$

$$x_1 = x_0 + \vec{v}_1\Delta t$$

And the scheme becomes:

$$\boxed{\text{Find } \vec{a}} \rightarrow \boxed{\text{Find } \vec{V}} \rightarrow \boxed{\text{Find } \vec{x}} \rightarrow \boxed{\text{Find the new } \vec{a}}$$

$$\vec{a}_n = -\vec{x}_n$$

$$v_{n+1}^{\vec{}} = v_n^{\vec{}} + \vec{a}_n\Delta t$$

$$x_{n+1} = x_n + v_{n+1}^{\vec{}}\Delta t$$

$$a_{n+1}^{\vec{}} = -x_{n+1}^{\vec{}}$$

At this point in the lecture, Feynman switches to leapfrog, although he never talks about the method itself [1, 2]. In his words, "We shall organize the work in a way that will increase the precision of our calculations, using the

same coarse time interval” [1]. He calculates the first velocity by using half of the step size. In other words, the average velocity value is calculated for the given time interval. After this adjustment, everything else is calculated with the original step size. Figure 1 illustrates this point nicely.

Time	0	t/2	t	3t/2	2t	5t/2	3t	7t/2	4t	9t/2	5t	11t/2
Position	x_0	→	x_1	→	x_2	→	x_3	→	x_4	→	x_5	
Velocity		v_1	→	v_2	→	v_3	→	v_4	→	v_5	→	v_6
Acceleration	a_0	→	a_1	→	a_2	→	a_3	→	a_4	→	a_5	

Figure 1: Leapfrog Scheme

$$\boxed{\vec{a}_0 = -\vec{x}_0} \rightarrow \boxed{\vec{a}_1 = -\vec{x}_1}$$

$$\boxed{\vec{v}_1 = \vec{v}_0 + \vec{a}_0 \frac{\Delta t}{2}} \rightarrow \boxed{\vec{v}_2 = \vec{v}_1 + \vec{a}_1 \Delta t}$$

$$\boxed{x_1 = x_0 + \vec{v}_1 \Delta t} \rightarrow \boxed{x_2 = x_1 + \vec{v}_2 \Delta t}$$

After giving this simple spring-mass system example, he moves on to the motion of the planets by using Newton’s law of gravity [4, 1]. In the previous chapter, we have already found the formula for acceleration 2. However, Feynman expands the vector equation of acceleration into their rectangular components [4, 1].

$$m_i \frac{dv_{ix}}{dx} = \sum_{j=1}^N -\frac{Gm_i m_j (x_i - x_j)}{r_{ij}^3}$$

$$m_i \frac{dv_{iy}}{dy} = \sum_{j=1}^N -\frac{Gm_i m_j (y_i - y_j)}{r_{ij}^3}$$

$$m_i \frac{dv_{iz}}{dz} = \sum_{j=1}^N -\frac{Gm_i m_j (z_i - z_j)}{r_{ij}^3}$$

Simplifying the equation yields the acceleration formula for each planet:

$$a_{ix} = \sum_{j=1}^N -\frac{k_j(x_i - x_j)}{r_{ij}^3}$$

$$a_{iy} = \sum_{j=1}^N -\frac{k_j(y_i - y_j)}{r_{ij}^3}$$

$$a_{iz} = \sum_{j=1}^N -\frac{k_j(z_i - z_j)}{r_{ij}^3}$$

Just as in the mass-spring system, the scheme becomes:

$$\boxed{\vec{a} = -\frac{k}{r^2}\hat{r}} \rightarrow \boxed{\vec{v} = \vec{a}t} \rightarrow \boxed{\vec{x} = \vec{v}t} \rightarrow \boxed{\vec{a} = -\frac{k}{r^2}\hat{r}}$$

At the time this lecture was being taught, the power of computers was almost non-existent compared to today's standards. In his book, he concludes the chapter with an amusing comment. "Now, armed with the tremendous power of Newton's laws, we can not only calculate such simple motions but also, given only a machine to handle the arithmetic, even the tremendously complex motions of the planets, to as high a degree of precision as we wish!" [4, 2].

4 Why Leapfrog?

Leapfrog is a symplectic integration method [8, 9, 10]. It always conserves the energy and the angular momentum of the system [11, 9, 8, 10]. Unlike other popular integration methods such as Runge-Kutta, which are non-symplectic and prone to accumulating errors over time [9], Leapfrog is immune to such errors. This makes it one of the best methods for simulations of any n-body system for extremely long periods.

5 JPL - A different way to test the accuracy of Leapfrog method

After finishing Feynman's chapter on the motion of the planets [4], I found myself wondering how one can test the accuracy of the leapfrog-generated

position data for each planet [1]. Of course, we can check the conservation of the energy and angular momentum of the system, but I also wanted to explore other options. Luckily, JPL has published ephemerides for almost every object in our solar system, relative to multiple reference frames, which are accessible through the Horizons system [12]. This allowed me to establish the inertial reference frame for the calculations. Among the available options, I chose the Solar System Barycenter in the rectangular coordinate system as the reference frame. This point serves as the center of mass of the entire solar system and is the point around which planets and the Sun orbit. I obtained the initial conditions of each planet from the JPL website and calculated the trajectory of each object. Doing the calculations by hand would take a lot of time and Feynman does this by hand to illustrate the point. You can find the handwriting in [2, 1]. However, I have written a code in Fortran to speed up the process. The code can be accessed from here [5].

6 Comparison of the JPL data with Leapfrog

To assess the validity of applying the leapfrog integration method to the motion of planets, this section will try to answer the following key questions. Is the total energy of the simulated system conserved? How well do the calculated planetary positions (in the rectangular coordinate system) compare to those provided by JPL? What is the impact of time step size on simulation accuracy?

There are 10 objects in the leapfrog simulation: The Sun, Mercury, Venus, the Earth-Moon System, Mars System, Jupiter System, Saturn System, Uranus System, Neptune System, and Pluto System. These systems represent the respective planets and their moons as a single point. In my first simulations, I have added the moons of each planet separately. However, this approach was computationally costly as more objects meant slower calculation. Thus, I opted for a simplified system as 10 objects are faster to simulate than 150 objects, taking the barycenter of each planet system to represent the whole system.

The leapfrog simulations of the solar system will use the following time durations with their corresponding time steps (Figure 2). All these simulations started at 00:00 TDB on February 8, 2024.

Time Duration	Time Step
1 year	1 second
1 year	10 seconds
1 year	100 seconds
10 years	10 seconds
10 years	100 seconds
100 years	1080 seconds
1000 years	1080 seconds

Figure 2: Simulation time durations and corresponding step sizes.

For these simulations, the total energy of the whole system is calculated at each time step. This involves summing the kinetic and potential energies of all celestial bodies. However, how can the energy of a n-body system be calculated? Before moving on to the n-body problem, it would be beneficial to consider a simpler two-body case. The total energy calculation in the 2-body problem is given in the following equation [6].

$$E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 - \frac{GMm}{r} \quad (3)$$

where:

$$K = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$$

$$P = -\frac{GMm}{r}$$

However, for the n-body problem, the calculation of the total energy changes. The potential energy and kinetic energy for the entire system are given in the following equations [11].

$$E = K_{\text{total}} + P_{\text{total}}$$

$$P_{\text{total}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{1, i \neq j}^N \frac{-GM_i M_j}{2r_{ij}}$$

$$K_{\text{total}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{2} m_i v_i^2$$

By utilizing these formulas, energy conservation in leapfrog simulations will be monitored. The relative change in energy, ΔE , will be calculated after each time step.

$$\Delta E = \frac{|E - E_0|}{E_0}$$

where:

$\Delta E \equiv$ Calculated relative energy change of the system

$E_0 \equiv$ Calculated energy of the system at the start of the simulation

$E \equiv$ Calculated energy of the system after each step

The angular momentum of the whole system is calculated using the following formula [11]:

$$L_{\text{total}}^{\vec{}} = \sum_{i=1}^N m_i (\vec{r}_i \times \vec{v}_i)$$

It will be monitored with the relative change in angular momentum, ΔL . It is calculated as:

$$\Delta L = \frac{|L - L_0|}{L_0}$$

where:

$\Delta L \equiv$ Calculated relative angular momentum change of the system

$L_0 \equiv$ Calculated angular momentum of the system at the start of the simulation

$L \equiv$ Calculated angular momentum of the system after each step

Lastly, to compare JPL's position data with the leapfrog position data, I have used the code written by my dear friend, Mert Çetin, whose code can be accessed from here. [3]

In the following sections, the relative change in system energy and angular momentum (ΔE and ΔL) over time will be presented for each case. The following figures will illustrate the positional discrepancies between the leapfrog simulation and JPL data for each celestial body.

6.1 Choosing the most accurate gravitational parameter for each planet

As previously discussed in chapter 2, the gravitational parameter is crucial to the simulation of the system. However, the gravitational parameters of each object are not exactly known and they are estimated using numerical methods based on satellite data. For this research, the most recent gravitational parameter values were obtained from NASA GMAT, JPL Horizons and academic papers [13, 12, 14].

6.2 Simulation of the Solar System (1 Year - 1 Seconds)

Figure 3: ΔE of the solar system

Figure 4: ΔL of the solar system

Figure 5: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for the Sun

Figure 6: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Mercury

Figure 7: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Venus

Figure 8: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for the Earth-Moon System

Figure 9: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Mars

Figure 10: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Jupiter

Figure 11: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Saturn System

Figure 12: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Uranus System

Figure 13: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Neptune System

Figure 14: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Pluto System

6.3 Simulation of the Solar System (1 Year - 10 Seconds)

Figure 15: ΔE of the solar system

Figure 16: ΔL of the solar system

Figure 17: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for the Sun

Figure 18: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Mercury

Figure 19: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Venus

Figure 20: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for the Earth-Moon System

Figure 21: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Mars

Figure 22: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Jupiter

Figure 23: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Saturn System

Figure 24: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Uranus System

Figure 25: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Neptune System

Figure 26: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Pluto System

6.4 Simulation of the Solar System (1 Year - 100 Seconds)

Figure 27: ΔE of the solar system

Figure 28: ΔL of the solar system

Figure 29: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for the Sun

Figure 30: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Mercury

Figure 31: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Venus

Figure 32: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for the Earth-Moon System

Figure 33: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Mars

Figure 34: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Jupiter

Figure 35: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Saturn System

Figure 36: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Uranus System

Figure 37: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Neptune System

Figure 38: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Pluto System

6.5 Simulation of the Solar System (10 Years - 10 Seconds)

Figure 39: ΔE of the solar system

Figure 40: ΔL of the solar system

Figure 41: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for the Sun

Figure 42: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Mercury

Figure 43: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Venus

Figure 44: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for the Earth-Moon System

Figure 45: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Mars

Figure 46: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Jupiter

Figure 47: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Saturn System

Figure 48: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Uranus System

Figure 49: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Neptune System

Figure 50: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Pluto System

6.6 Simulation of the Solar System (10 Years - 100 Seconds)

Figure 51: ΔE of the solar system

Figure 52: ΔL of the solar system

Figure 53: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for the Sun

Figure 54: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Mercury

Figure 55: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Venus

Figure 56: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for the Earth-Moon System

Figure 57: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Mars

Figure 58: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Jupiter

Figure 59: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Saturn System

Figure 60: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Uranus System

Figure 61: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Neptune System

Figure 62: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Pluto System

6.7 Simulation of the Solar System (100 Years - 1080 Seconds)

Figure 63: ΔE of the solar system

Figure 64: ΔL of the solar system

Figure 65: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for the Sun

Figure 66: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Mercury

Figure 67: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Venus

Figure 68: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for the Earth-Moon System

Figure 69: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Mars

Figure 70: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Jupiter

Figure 71: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Saturn System

Figure 72: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Uranus System

Figure 73: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Neptune System

Figure 74: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Pluto System

6.8 Simulation of the Solar System (1000 Years - 1080 Seconds)

Figure 75: ΔE of the solar system

Figure 76: ΔL of the solar system

Figure 77: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for the Sun

Figure 78: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Mercury

Figure 79: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Venus

Figure 80: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for the Earth-Moon System

Figure 81: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Mars

Figure 82: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Jupiter

Figure 83: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Saturn System

Figure 84: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Uranus System

Figure 85: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Neptune System

Figure 86: Positional Difference Between Leapfrog and JPL Position for Pluto System

7 Conclusion

The analysis of planetary positions generated by the leapfrog method, compared to the data provided by JPL, revealed discrepancies that increased with simulation time. While the method demonstrated reasonable energy and angular momentum conservation, the positional inaccuracies compared to JPL's suggest the need for further investigation into factors such as relativistic effects, numerical errors, potential uncertainties in the adopted gravitational parameters, and others. Pinpointing the exact source of error requires further investigation. However, all stepsize output agreed reasonably well with the JPL's position data for the first few days. Another crucial aspect of this analysis is that as objects got further away from the Sun, they experienced less deviation from the JPL's published ephemerides.

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